

TRANSFORMATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES

FOR
**PEOPLE
OCEAN
PLANET**

**BIODIVERSITY &
NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS**

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Transformational Opportunities in Deploying Biodiversity Conservation Initiatives and Nature-Based Solutions to Address Climate Change in Marine Ecosystems

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Executive Summary

Climate change threatens the health of marine ecosystems and their capacity to support biodiversity and human wellbeing. Nature-based solutions (NbS), involving protection, restoration and sustainable management, provide cost-effective and sustainable transformational opportunities to mitigate and adapt to climate change, while also supporting biodiversity and, in many cases, supporting and protecting local livelihoods. A range of NbS, both long-established and new, have been implemented in coastal and marine areas. However, with a few exceptions these tend to be project-based and with almost negligible effects for climate mitigation at a globally significant level, and only local potential for climate change adaptation.

This paper focuses on identifying transformational opportunities that could enable marine NbS to be deployed at a scale that would make a substantive contribution to climate change mitigation and adaptation. The opportunities may be in identifying new types of NbS, but particularly may be in creating new mechanisms that facilitate scaling of solutions from local to regional or global.

We also outline a number of ‘guiding principles’ or ‘best practices’ that would apply to all the actions we identify. These include that all proposed innovations in NbS should be: contextual (e.g., determined by cultural and natural contexts); co-produced/reflective of values (e.g., by relevant traditional, local, scientific knowledge holders); and embedded in recognition, procedural and distributional justice.

The selected transformational opportunities are: (1) Leveraging the data revolution to build resilient reefs in the face of increasing climate change; (2) Supporting Indigenous Stewardship; (3) Implementing the high seas as a marine protected area; (4) Change in social norms: transformational narratives for ocean action; (5) Blue carbon ecosystem finance; and (6) Financing coastal risk reduction. The TOP Changes in social norms TOP is cross-cutting and can be used to amplify other TOPS. In addition, we emphasize the need to enhance Blue Biodiversity Investments and propose a contribution to the Tetiaroa project, in the form of rReconnecting land-sea nutrient feedbacks to enhance island ecosystem resilience.

Focus and Scope

The core question we seek to address in this paper is: *How can innovations in designing, implementing and scaling nature-based solutions, including biodiversity conservation, help to address climate change and increase ecosystem health?*

A range of NbS, both long-established and new, have been implemented in coastal and marine areas. However, with a few exceptions these tend to be project-based and with almost negligible effects for climate mitigation at a globally significant level, and only local potential for climate change adaptation.

This paper focuses on identifying transformational opportunities that could enable marine biodiversity conservation initiatives and NbS to be deployed at a scale that would make a substantive contribution to climate change mitigation and adaptation, and on their enabling conditions. As a guiding principles, all proposed transformational opportunities should be:

- Contextual (e.g., determined by cultural & natural contexts)
- Co-produced/reflective of local values (e.g., by relevant traditional, local, scientific knowledge holders; Turner et al., 2008; Jupiter et al., 2014)
- Embedded in recognitional, procedural & distributive justice (e.g., Jupiter et al. 2014, Bennett et al. 2019)

Definitions

Nature-Based Solutions:

In defining nature-based solutions for this paper, we broadly align with the IUCN definition and recent global standards (IUCN, n.d.), that is: *“Actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits.”* IUCN (2012)

However, to consider novel opportunities, we adopt an element of the European Commission definition,

which includes technological solutions “copied from nature”: *“Nature-based solutions aim to help societies address a variety of environmental, social and economic challenges in sustainable ways. They are actions inspired by, supported by or copied from nature; both using and enhancing existing solutions to challenges, as well as exploring more novel solutions, for example, mimicking how non-human organisms and communities cope with environmental extremes”* (EC 2015)

It is important to recognise that nature-based solutions only have limited potential to mitigate climate change, because the magnitude of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions is so large that the primary solution has to come from reduction of fossil fuel related emissions to close to zero. NbS can contribute to climate change mitigation by compensation for hard-to-eliminate emissions, but cannot be viewed as a panacea to address climate change. In particular, if they are promoted as an “offset” that permits business-as-usual high carbon emission activities, they could actually be damaging for long-term climate and biodiversity prospects. Where they do contribute to climate change mitigation, they have the potential to provide ecological, social and economic co-benefits. NbS also play a vital role in protecting people and economic sectors from the impacts of climate change by supporting adaptation, and these benefits can be important regardless of their contribution to climate change mitigation (Chausson et al. 2020).

Transformational Opportunities:

To frame the notion of transformational opportunities, we employ the definition used by Kates et al. (2012). They define transformational adaptation opportunities as those that: 1) are adopted at scale and 2) are new to a region or resource system.

Transformational Opportunity Areas

Here, we present 6 key Transformational Opportunities (TOPS 1-6), emphasize the need for an enhanced Blue biodiversity investment (Box 1), and propose a contribution to the Tetiaroa project (Box 2).

1. Leveraging the data revolution to build resilient reefs in the face of increasing climate change

Description:

Coral reefs globally have declined significantly due to a combination of climate change and other human stressors. In the last three decades, over half of the world's shallow-water coral reefs have been lost. The increasing frequency and intensity of mass bleaching events is making it harder for coral reefs to recover naturally as there is less time and capacity between events to support recovery (Hoegh-Guldberg et al. 2007; Montefalcone et al. 2018). In addition, chronic disturbances to coral reefs adversely affect larval supply, settlement, and recruitment of coral larvae and post-settlement survival (Richmond 1993; Fabricius et al. 2017). Therefore, the potential of restoration is increasingly explored to jump-start a reef's capacity to recover from disturbance. Restoration helps to restore the structure and function of the coral reef ecosystem and supports ecosystem resilience.

However, ecosystem restoration often occurs with high rates of failure (Bayraktarov et al. 2016) due to inadequate consideration of the threats occurring across the system leading to ecosystem decline. Similarly, coral reef restoration often focuses on coral structure and fails to include the wider seascape, despite the recognition of the importance of an ecosystem-based approach. Incorporating wider ecological patterns and processes into restoration planning is recognized as a fundamental component of successful restoration (Ladd et al. 2018) and resilience-based management (Bell et al. 1997, Gilby et al. 2018; Mcleod et al. 2019). Therefore, a holistic approach is needed to identify,

protect, and restore areas most resilient to changing ocean conditions, while rehabilitating seascape structure and functions to better manage reefs in perpetuity.

[Recent innovations in remote sensing](#) provide the opportunity to shift restoration goals from single habitat restoration efforts to seascape restoration, resulting in lasting positive outcomes. Where the health of seascapes is tightly coupled to the condition of adjacent terrestrial landscapes, the approach must also consider land-sea connectivity where stress mitigation actions may be required to achieve restoration outcomes. The unique and multi-scaled combination of Planetscope satellite constellations (global), [Global Airborne Observatory](#) (GAO) data (regional) and drone imagery (local), coupled with big data computation can provide reef managers with a new and powerful toolkit to better inform coral restoration out-planting efforts, evaluate exposure to stress and track progress over time. This cutting-edge technology offers unprecedented potential to advance spatial prioritization of coral reef restoration, for example, through the identification of optimal locations for reef restoration based on sites with the greatest potential to be more resilient to climate impacts. Restoration frameworks that are integrative and multi-scale and that explicitly consider the seascape context, the spatial arrangement of habitat and ecological connectivity (i.e., marine and ridge to reef) can help to guide ecologically meaningful actions and reduce uncertainty in restoration outcomes.

An opportunity exists to identify and map key indicators of coral survival and resilience to inform coral restoration design. The integration of new remote sensing technology and machine learning can be used to advance spatial prioritization of coral reef restoration and document changes in restoration sites (i.e., benthic community, reef condition). Through applying a seascape ecology approach, it will be possible, for the first time, to connect ecological patterns and processes into restoration planning and establish a framework for scaling up restoration design to encompass important seascape patterns and processes that determine the long-term resilience of investments. Seascape ecology, a newly emerging pattern-oriented science (Pittman 2018; Wedding et al. 2011) offers great potential to inform the effective design of coastal restoration strate-

gies. To support greater uptake, it will be important to integrate this new approach into a tool to help managers prioritize areas for restoration, assess threats to restoration success, identify areas where ecological connectivity has been disrupted due to habitat loss or degradation to inform rehabilitation efforts, and explore co-benefits of reef restoration to adjacent down-stream reefs. This novel seascape approach will advance the field of coastal restoration to move from a single habitat approach to a broader whole-system approach that considers climate impacts, ecological function, seascape connectivity, and ecosystem service benefits to coastal communities.

Proposed Outcomes:

Reef restoration is identified as an essential management approach to improve coral reef condition. Proposed outcomes could include increased coral cover in areas projected to be more resilient to climate impacts, recovery of ecosystem structure and function, and increased marine biodiversity and ecosystem services. Ecosystem service benefits derived from reef restoration include an increase in fisheries, jobs, tourism, coastal protection, and marine biodiversity. To ensure the sustainability of these benefits, project results will be monitored through an adaptive management framework (Thom et al. 2005) to learn from these experiments and assess the effectiveness of restoration efforts.

Benefits:

Climate mitigation/adaptation: Mostly climate adaptation benefits.

Timing of benefits: The length of time for restored reefs to provide adaptation benefits depends on the local social, climatic, oceanographic, and ecological characteristics of the site, including the frequency and severity of disturbances, the restoration technique utilized (microfragmentation, larval propagation, structural support, etc.; Boström-Einarsson et al. 2020) and the objectives of the restoration project but often ranges between 5-10 years.

Climate benefit: Reef restoration supports adaptation to climate change (Roberts et al., 2017) as reefs can provide coastal protection benefits to coastal commu-

nities in the face of increasing storms and sea-level rise; healthy fish stocks dependent on reefs supports food security; and alternative livelihood opportunities, such as reef tourism, may generate income for local communities.

Co-benefits: Out-planting coral fragments is increasingly implemented to aid coral population rescue, with the long-term goal of restoring reef ecosystem function and services. Many human well-being benefits of coral restoration have been documented including: provision of alternative livelihood opportunities, educational opportunities, building stewardship, maintenance of wellbeing, identity, place attachment, aesthetics and pride around resource condition, and restoring agency regarding the use and management of natural resources (Hein et al. 2019).

Equity and distribution: Mapping products and quantitative online tools could be made freely available and allow restoration practitioners and local governments to prioritize coral-outplanting restoration sites that maximize multiple key ecological services (i.e. coastal protection, fisheries, and tourism contributing to the local economy) to coastal communities and support coral recovery from habitat and biotic community monitoring data.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: The costs of reef restoration are highly variable based on what costs are considered (e.g., capital, operating, in-kind costs., etc.), restoration technique (e.g., direct transplantation, larval enhancement, coral gardening, substrate stabilization, etc.), control of existing stressors at site that affect restoration success, and the restoration objective (endangered species recover, coastal protection, restoring ecosystem function). A recent analysis (Bayraktarov et al. 2019) reported that median reef restoration costs were ~400,000 US\$/ha with a high end of the range at 4,000,000 US\$/ha. An analysis focusing on the Mexican-Caribbean estimated reef restoration costs between US\$100,000 – US\$500,000/ha considering about 10,000 transplants per hectare, although long-term monitoring costs were not considered (Zepeda-Centeno et al. 2018).

Return on Investment: The number and scale of coral

out-planting projects has rapidly increased, yet very few (if any) programs are rigorously evaluating and operationalizing ecological design elements that enhance coral survival and growth following out-planting. High return on investment can be demonstrated when benefits related to coastal habitat restoration, fisheries and climate change mitigation are considered.

Barriers: Part of the challenge has been technical capacity to quantify and forecast large-scale ecological processes across the seascape— until now. The science and capacity to map and monitor benthic habitats that make up marine seascapes has matured rapidly, in particular the application of tools such as remote sensing and geographic information systems (GIS) to creating detailed map-based audits of marine environments up to national and regional scales (Rowlands et al. 2012; Schill et al. 2011; Knudby et al. 2014).

Feasibility: There has been significant investment in the development and refinement of innovative coral restoration techniques. Strong partnerships between NGO’s, communities, researchers, and government, including restoration capacity on the ground, will provide critical enabling conditions for success. The availability of recent high resolution (1 m) remotely sensed-derived products provide an excellent test bed to evaluate reef conditions and criteria for restoration success.

Minimal risk: Low potential for negative side effects.

2. Supporting Indigenous Stewardship

Description:

Most of the focus in climate change mitigation, adaptation, and NbS literature stems from Western scientific endeavors, whereas Indigenous peoples have thousands of years of oral histories and place-based knowledge of adapting to climate change and stewarding their territories (Sterling et al. 2017; 2020; Chausson et al. 2020). As climate change threatens more of the world’s communities and ecosystems,

Two globally relevant ways of supporting Indigenous stewardship are through:

1. Indigenous Guardian programs
2. Rights of nature

First, as part of a more recent operationalization of long-held Indigenous stewardship, many Indigenous nations have developed Indigenous Guardian programs (also called Indigenous Rangers in some places). Such programs, designed by and for Indigenous peoples, commonly provide training, jobs, equipment, and other resources to enable Indigenous peoples to be the eyes and ears on their territories. They ensure rules and laws are followed, and they provide a way to reconnect people to their territories and revitalize stewardship and cultural practices. For instance, the [Coastal Guardian Watchmen program in British Co-](#)

Figure 1. Coral reef mapping products from local to global scales.

[lumbia](#), Canada, provides a marine-based stewardship initiative and includes procurement of boats, training, and funds for staff. This effort has expanded to develop the [Indigenous Guardians Toolkit](#), which has guides to enable other Indigenous nations to create their own guardian programs. Additional funds could make an enormous difference in empowering coastal Indigenous nations around the world to steward and monitor their marine and coastal territories.

Second, there are several Indigenous-led efforts to assign legal rights to nature that, if expanded, would shift how natural resources are managed. For example, in New Zealand, the Whanganui River has received statutory recognition as Te Awa Tupua and given legal rights as a living being and entity in its own right, with guardianship Te Pou Tupua jointly appointed by the crown and the Indigenous Iwi to represent the River in human decision-making processes (Hsaio 2012). This model, though time-consuming to put in place, could be adopted elsewhere to provide durable provision of multiple ecosystem services and biodiversity protection from NbS.

Furthermore, there are vast opportunities to support place-based NbS efforts by Indigenous peoples to adapt to climate change. For example, along parts of the Pacific Northwest Coast of North America, Indig-

enous peoples have actively managed intertidal clam beds, referred to as clam gardens, for thousands of years (Toniello et al. 2019). Through the construction of rock terraces, selective harvesting, and soil aeration among other practices, clam gardens extended and enhanced clam habitat to provide an abundant and predictable food source (Deur et al. 2015). In addition, clam gardens can dissipate wave energy - acting as submerged breakwaters - and can, therefore, be characterized as effective NbS for adaptation to sea level rise in coastal communities (Lokman and Tomkins, 2020). Clam gardens provide a context-specific example of the -benefits - for biodiversity, climate adaptation, and food security - generated through the revitalization of Indigenous coastal management practices (Cox et al. 2019, Groesback et al. 2014). A fund for Indigenous adaptation through self-determined NbS would support diverse and locally appropriate adaptation.

Benefits:

Climate mitigation/adaptation: This TOPS focuses on climate change adaptation, and benefits biodiversity.

Climate-benefit: The primary benefit is locally-relevant climate adaptation that also benefits biodiversity and supports Indigenous governance. Through en-

Figure 2. Coastal Guardian Watchmen boat in Heiltsuk territory on the central coast of what is now known as British Columbia, Canada.

environmental stewardship, it may also support small-scale climate mitigation.

Co-benefits: By empowering Indigenous efforts, Indigenous peoples and environmental stewardship will benefit, for example through active management, restoration efforts, improved compliance, monitoring that can facilitate adaptive management. Natural structures (clam gardens, fish ponds) can also provide co-benefits (coastal protection) and their restoration can serve as a nature-based solution.

Equity and distribution: This TOPS is specifically designed to support equity by focusing on stewardship efforts by Indigenous peoples.

Timing of benefits: This solution can provide benefits starting in the short term, and will benefits will extend into the long term. Within a couple of years of starting up these projects and related restoration/infrastructure/training, adaptation solutions will begin to garner benefits. Specific timing will depend on locally selected solutions and will vary.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: Low compared to other TOPS. The main cost is training, capacity (e.g., hiring people, supporting learning exchanges), and infrastructure (e.g., boats for Guardian programs).

Return on investment: High return on investment, as this TOPS supports biodiversity conservation, climate adaptation, and equity considerations, with many co-benefits.

Barriers: The cost to start up Indigenous guardian programs and Indigenous NbS is the main barrier to enabling Indigenous peoples to enhance their stewardship; funding could remove this barrier.

Feasibility: This TOPS is highly feasible. The technologies exist, and Indigenous peoples around the world are seeking to revitalize their own stewardship and NbS. However, in addition, in some countries Indigenous peoples continue to be deliberately marginalized, and thus political barriers may exist.

Risk: There is minimal risk of negative side effects.

3. Implementing the high seas as a marine protected area

Description:

A healthy ocean is critical for human well-being. Many Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) may not be met without achieving SDG 14 for ocean conservation and sustainable use (Singh et al., 2018; Claudet et al., 2020a). However, oceans are threatened by multiple direct stressors; direct exploitation of organisms, mainly fishing, being the most impactful driver (Díaz et al., 2019). While there is an urgent need to modify human behavior to allow sustainable development pathways (Butchart et al. 2010; Nash et al. 2017), mitigation strategies still need to be put into practice.

Marine protected areas (MPAs) are an effective spatial, ecosystem-based management tool to protect biodiversity (Lubchenco and Grorud-Colvert, 2015). An MPA is a marine area geographically defined, established by international, national, territorial, tribal or local law, designated to improve the long-term conservation of its biodiversity and natural resources. Ecological and fisheries effects of MPAs have been extensively studied by scientists worldwide. Inside their borders, MPAs can usually increase abundance, size, biomass and diversity of species (Lester et al., 2009) and contribute to re-establishing population, community and habitat structure (Babcock et al., 2010). Outside their borders, benefits can spill over, potentially contributing to fisheries catch (Di Lorenzo et al., 2016; 2020).

Member States Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) agreed to cover 10% of their Economic Exclusive Zones (EEZs) by MPAs by 2020 (CBD, 2010). This areal target is identified in target 5 of SDG 14. However, observed protection, accounting for established MPAs is presently 3.6% (Sala et al. 2018a). The current system of MPAs falls short in covering adequately specific species geographical range (Davidon and Dulvy, 2017; Guilhaumon et al., 2015). In addition, a significant proportion of those MPAs do not have the sufficient levels of protection (Claudet et al. 2020b; Zupan et al. 2018), management capacity (Gill et al. 2017) or enforcement (Guidetti et al. 2018) to be fully effective. A recent synthesis showed that to

(1) efficiently protect biodiversity; (2) ensure population connectivity among MPAs; (3) minimize the risk of fisheries/population collapse and ensure population persistence; (4) mitigate the adverse evolutionary effects of fishing; (5) maximize or optimize fisheries value or yield; and (6) satisfy multiple stakeholders, at least 30% of the ocean should be protected (O’Leary et al., 2016).

While the 30% target now being considered for the CBD post-2020 Agendas, some even advocate that these targets should be raised to 50% (half-earth) (Ellis 2019). The 50% target is now debated in the scientific community (Díaz et al. 2020) and still lacks a consensus on how it should be operationalized at a planetary scale, mostly because at least one billion people live in places that would be protected if the Half Earth proposal were implemented within all ecoregions (Schleicher et al., 2019).

However, at the ocean scale, some recent evidence are converging about the benefits of protecting very large, inhabited portions of the ocean, such as the high seas (or areas beyond national jurisdiction) (Wright et al., 2018), where the human footprint is increasing at a worrying pace (Jouffray et al., 2020; Levin et al., 2020). Although the approach would be different than protecting 50% of each marine ecoregion, this would represent protecting almost half of our planet (Figure 3). Evidence supporting the implementation of the high seas as an MPAs include:

1. The high seas are the waters beyond any country’s national jurisdiction, they make up 64% of the entire ocean, 45% of the total surface of the Earth -and 95% of its volume.
2. The open ocean provides an underappreciated \$8000Bn a year in ecosystem services (Costanza et al. 2018).
3. The ocean plankton produces more than 20% of the oxygen in our entire biosphere; more than all of the tropical rainforests on land combined.
4. The high seas are heavily impacted by climate change (IPCC, 2019), fishing (FAO, 2020), and more and more activities such as seabed mining, geo-engineering, and aquaculture are being considered in the high seas (Jouffray et al. 2020).

5. Up to 54% of high seas fishing would be unprofitable without government subsidies (Sala et al. 2018b). Furthermore exploited labour (i.e., human rights abuses) and unreported fishing may explain how other large vessels afford to fish in international waters.
6. Protecting the high seas can increase future catch and food provisioning through spillover in adjacent exploited areas (Cabral et al., in press; Marshall et al., 2019).
7. More than 43% of the blue carbon extracted by fisheries in the high seas comes from areas that would be economically unprofitable without subsidies (Mariani et al. in press). Limiting blue carbon extraction by fisheries, particularly on unprofitable areas, would reduce CO2 emissions by burning less fuel and reactivating a natural carbon pump through the rebuilding of fish stocks and the increase of carcasses deadfall.
8. The soon to be finalized UN treaty for the conservation of biodiversity in the high seas will allow to establish MPAs in the high seas, with political will. Several Small Island Developing States (SIDSs) support the idea of protecting the high seas.

Benefits:

Climate benefit: Marine protected areas help mitigating climate change by promoting carbon sequestration and storage and adapting to climate change by increasing resilience of protected ecosystems and by buffering against uncertainty in management, environmental fluctuations, directional change, and extreme events (Roberts et al., 2017).

Co-benefits: In addition to the range of well-being benefits of marine protected areas (Ban et al., 2019), protecting the high seas can have direct positive benefits on fisheries at national levels (Cabral et al. in press; Sala et al., 2018b;) and on nutrition (Hicks et al., 2019).

Equity and distribution: In addition to spillover effects inside national waters of adjacent countries, the sharing of benefits of protecting the high seas can be designed within the corresponding section in the ongoing negotiations of an international legally binding in-

NEGLECTED WATERS

Almost two-thirds of the planet's ocean are classed as international waters or high seas, meaning that they are beyond the control of any one state.

Figure 3: The high seas, or areas beyond national jurisdictions, are increasingly threatened and represent almost half of our planet (taken from Wright et al. 2018).

strument under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction (Wright et al., 2018). Protecting the high seas would also potentially lead to greater equity in deriving benefits from highly mobile fish stocks, as distant water fishing nations would no longer be able to access and catch without paying licensing fees.

Timing of benefits: Marine protected areas have rapid and lasting effects (Babcock et al., 2010). Conservation and climate change adaptation benefits will occur faster than climate change mitigation and fisheries benefits.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: Closing the high seas to fishing is viable economically and should also lead to stopping fisheries

subsidies (Sala et al., 2018b). Additional costs would depend on the activities that are also restricted (Levin et al., 2020) and on enforcement costs.

Return on Investment: High return on investment related to fisheries and climate change mitigation and adaptation benefits.

Barriers: Legal tools to manage the high seas are being designed as an international legally binding instrument under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity of areas beyond national jurisdiction. Area-based management tools, including marine protected areas, will be one element of the treaty. However, this future BBNJ COP, as written in the current status of treaty under negotiation, cannot undermine actions of sectoral and regional management organizations, including regional fisheries management organizations or the International Seabed authority. What is needed is just a strong will of the countries that are both Parties to the future BBNJ COP and members of sectoral and regional management organizations.

Feasibility: What is needed is the political will of the countries that are both Parties to the future BBNJ COP and members of sectoral and regional management organizations to engage for the future of our next generations.

Risk: Low potential for negative side effects

4. Changing social norms: transformational narratives for ocean action

Description:

The ocean is so central to realizing sustainable futures that it is time for new narratives for the ocean, narratives that fosters ocean empathy and return the ocean to the center of our lives (Lubchenco and Gaines 2019, Brown et al. 2019). New narratives would shift collective perceptions of the ocean as an endless source of resources towards understanding the ocean as a finite and integral part of our daily lives, which could provide solutions to climate change. Such a change of perspective can help foster new social norms that will

incentivize governments, the private sector, and civil society groups and individuals to take necessary actions to protect, manage, and restore the ocean (Lubchenco et al. 2016). In the context of climate change, it is widely acknowledged that perceptions, emotions, and social norms, rather than objective information, play the decisive role in motivating climate action (Chapman et al. 2017; Fløttum and Gjerstad 2017; Hulme 2009; Moser 2010). Social norms provide impetus for collective action and can affect whether a policy succeeds (Ostrom, 2000, Kinzig et al. 2013). In fact, changing ‘the mindset or paradigm out of which the system - its goals, structure, rules, delays, parameters - arises’ has been identified as one of the most powerful places to intervene in a system to leverage change for sustainability (Meadows 1999, Abson et al. 2017, O’Brien 2018, Figure 4a). Changing social norms about the ocean may offer a less obvious, but potentially powerful entry point to support the implementation of nature-based solutions in coastal and marine areas. It is important to note that this TOP can thus be used on its own or as a catalyzer, or amplifier, of the other TOPS described in this document.

Before introducing several practical mechanisms for fostering new social norms, two points warrant clarification. First, social norms are highly diverse. We do not advocate for the imposition of certain values and worldviews on others in culturally or ethically intrusive ways. In the context of rapid biodiversity loss and climate change, it is increasingly important to move towards a “diverse conservation ethic; one that recognizes and accepts all values of nature, from intrinsic to instrumental, and welcomes all philosophies justifying nature protection and restoration, from ethical to economic, and from aesthetic to utilitarian” (Tallis and Lubchenco, 2014, p. 27). However, anthropocentric viewpoints, where human well-being is dissociated from environmental integrity, have been identified as a root driver of contemporary sustainability challenges (Folke et al. 2011, Ives et al. 2018). Here, we subscribe to the empathy-sustainability hypothesis, which proposes that fostering empathy for the non-human world is a prerequisite for sustainable interactions with the biosphere (Brown et al. 2019).

Second, the purpose of changing social norms is not

about changing peoples’ individual behaviour per se. There is a risk that focusing on individual behaviour can divert attention from deeper, more structural changes necessary to tackle the climate crisis (Blythe et al. 2018). The goal of fostering new social norms is to create enabling conditions for systemic action that addresses the root drivers of climate change (O’Brien 2018). For example, increasing ocean empathy could catalyze cross scalar actions to protect coastal and marine ecosystems (Laffoley et al., in press). Growing public support for ocean stewardship can be mobilized into political pressure for more equitable and effective environmental policies and regulations (Martinez-Alier et al. 2016).

Two cost effective pathways for changing social norms to support NbS at scale include:

1. Future scenario visualizations.
2. Science communication.

First, visualizing futures scenarios can be a first step in creating new social norms and commitments that enable radical transformations toward sustainability (Pereira et al. 2018). As Bai et al. (2016, p. 359) challenged us to consider, “scenarios have been positioned at the end of an argument... but what if scenarios were taken as the *starting point* for the argument?”. In other words, broader use of future scenarios in public deliberations and collective decision-making could support radically new perspectives and support for NbS. Visualizations, ranging from art to web apps to virtual reality, offer effective tools for bringing future scenarios to life (Figure 4b). For example, visualizations can increase public support for shoreline hardening to reduce coastal flood risk towards NbS for coastal protection. The ‘Coastline Change: Future Scenarios’ app, for example, allows users to explore how climate change combined with management actions over a 50-year time frame may affect the rates of shoreline change (<https://coastalresilience.org/project/coastline-change-future-scenarios/>). In Canada, web-based visualizations tools are being used to stimulate support (from local to upper levels of government) for NbS (Minano et al. 2018). In China, flood simulations in virtual reality are being used to encourage support for

Figure 4. a) Leverage points for system change and their relationship to O'Brien's (2018) practical, political, and personal spheres of transformations. The personal sphere (which includes social norms) is theorized to hold the greatest potential for catalyzing societal change. b) Science communication tools, including videos, augmented reality, and virtual reality, can change peoples' perspectives and behaviour (photo: J Blythe).

low impact development (Wang et al. 2019). Finally, researchers from the Stockholm Resilience Centre have partnered with concept artists to produce future ocean narratives and accompanying paintings “because our oceans matter and we need new narratives to #saveourocean and guide efforts to transform towards more sustainable ocean governance” (Merrie et al. 2018). The paintings and narratives were featured at the 71st Session of the United Nations General Assembly, during the UN Oceans #saveourocean SDG 14 meeting in June 2017 (<https://radicaloceanfutures.earth/>).

Second, science communication campaigns have proven incredibly effective for changing collective norms and influencing policy change. For example, recent social media campaigns against single-use plastic have galvanized a global movement. At the time of writing, the YouTube video of a straw being removed from the nose of a marine sea turtle has been viewed more than 47 million times. The #stopsucking campaign, which aims to eradicate plastic pollution in the ocean, has garnered over 830 million social media impressions (<https://shortyawards.com/10th/strawless-ocean-campaign>). The surge in public disapproval of single-use plastic has led governments and corporations to ban single-use plastics straws in a matter of months (Schnurr et al. 2018). Short videos can also shape people's views and actions. In a study of video-based interventions in Ethiopia, evidence showed

that videos changed people's mental models or their belief in what is possible for the future (Bernard et al., 2014).

Benefits:

Climate benefit: Changing social norms could support both mitigation and adaptation. For example, shifting norms towards fossil fuels or sustainability fishing becoming socially unacceptable would support mitigation; demanding a new normal of NbS coastal standards would support adaptation.

Co-benefits: Changing social norms and behaviors should support a wide array of social and ecological benefits, including human health and improved nutrition.

Equity and distribution: Social benefits induced by changes in social norms will be differentially distributed (Daw et al. 2011, Bennett et al. 2019, Blythe et al. 2018).

Timing of benefits: Changing social norms can take decades (Westley and McGowan 2017). However, recent public outcry over single use plastic - and the resulting policy changes - provides evidence about how quickly global norms can change (Schnurr et al. 2018). While implementing government and corporate bans on single use plastic is considerably more ‘do-able’ than global decarbonization, it nevertheless provides

an important example of how quickly public opinion can change, and influence environmental policy.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: Changing social norms to support ocean NbS can be highly cost effective. Changing behaviour (and ultimately what is considered socially acceptable) through social media campaigns can be much less costly than other projects. For example, according to the Lonely Whale, their #stopsucking campaign cost \$0 and has garnered more than 830 million social media impressions.

Return on Investment: High

Barriers: Inertia in social structures and worldviews

Feasibility: High

Risk: Low

5. Blue carbon ecosystem finance

Description:

Blue carbon ecosystems, such as mangroves, seagrasses and salt marshes, are among the most effective natural carbon sinks (Murdiyarso, 2018), whilst also reducing the impacts of climate change on communities and infrastructure (Chausson et al. 2020; Seddon et al. 2020). However, their protection and restoration lacks effective funding mechanisms. To address this gap, we suggest adopting an integrated approach that is aligned with the real world of commercial finance, as well as with modern sustainability science and nature-based solutions. This approach, based on considering blue natural capital as an emerging asset class with long-term resilience value and multiple potential revenue streams, will bring money at scale to the sector, reduce barriers to entrance and cost to build a viable support infrastructure that reflects local needs.

The blue carbon sector has made significant progress (Crooks et al, 2017) in recent years in the scientific assessment of the mitigation benefits, with detailed data now available and new business cases (Flint et al, 2018). As a result of multiple initiatives (e.g., bluecarbonpartnership.org, cipicfinance.com), common policy approaches are now emerging, such as the in-

creased use of blue carbon commitments in Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), active community engagement in multiple countries and rising investor interest. Yet, in order to transition investment to scale the multiple additional benefits of blue carbon ecosystems beyond the pure climate mitigation aspects such as the adaptation, resilience and biodiversity impacts need to be bundled effectively (see bluenaturalcapital.org) with the delivery of livelihood benefits and community revenue streams, based on clear governance (Slobodian et al, 2019). By moving beyond addressing these aspects purely as qualitatively described co-benefits to quantifying their significant economic and financial impacts, it will be possible to bring to bear financial tools and markets to help build a sustainable blue natural capital asset class. Initial blended finance and results-based approaches need to be augmented to transition to a self-sustaining blue carbon ecosystem finance community. Integrating this approach with blue infrastructure finance concepts based on NBS (Thiele et al, 2020) and progress in implementing carbon accounting (PCAF, 2018) will provide opportunities to develop this pathway.

With market tools and resources now developed, it is possible to connect blue carbon ecosystems restoration and conservation efforts to market incentives for both the climate mitigation and resilience benefits these ecosystems provide. For instance, newly launched tools like the Global Mangrove Watch (globalmangrovetwatch.org) can support identification of vulnerable mangrove habitats at risk of deforestation. It is then possible to work with local communities to incorporate sustainable mangrove practices and develop market-based projects that can generate carbon offsets and resilience credits for purchase, providing a source of sustained funding to ensure long term habitat success.

Over the next several years, nations are working to map out their climate policies and expand on their NDCs to achieve Paris Agreement goals. It is important that all blue carbon ecosystems are included in these frameworks now, recognizing the important role they play in climate mitigation, coastal resilience, supporting economies, and safeguarding biodiversity. Governments need access to the most up-to-date blue

carbon ecosystems science and satellite habitat mapping, to support the inclusion of all blue carbon ecosystems into national climate policies.

Benefits:

Climate benefit: Significant net positive impact for mitigating/adapting to climate change as blue carbon ecosystems not only provide some of the highest carbon sinks per hectare but also deliver storm attenuation and flood management. Through this approach the full economic and social value of these climate services can be priced in and thus deliver a significant effort to maintain these.

Co-benefits: Local communities need these ecosystems to stay resilient in the face of climate change impacts, they help with food security, for instance through crab farming in mangroves and other fish nursery opportunities and offer multiple employment options such as ecosystem restoration and ecotourism work. Creating incentives to maintain blue carbon ecosystems leads to biodiversity protection as these are very diverse systems.

Equity and distribution: Direct benefits to go to local communities, with particular opportunities to benefit women who are for instance widely engaged in seaweed farming.

Timing of benefits: Significant immediate benefits, in particular since the most of the carbon is in the subsoil and unless protected will be released rapidly.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: The upfront investment cost will depend on the acreage involved and the degree of degradation but in most locations the creation of additional income flows beyond carbon credits will make these investments commercially viable. Blue natural capital is an investable proposition, though there can be upfront project development cost that may require grant support.

Return on Investment: High ratio of impact to cost.

Barriers: The past approach of treating blue carbon as a commodity that purely competed with other carbon sinks meant that this area received less investment than other carbon offsets such as solar PV etc. The lo-

cation of many blue carbon ecosystems in developing countries has meant that other risk factors such as legal and political aspects make investment difficult. In addition, some blue carbon ecosystems (e.g., seagrass) are still very poorly mapped, and carbon storage potential is still very poorly quantified.

Feasibility: Given the role of blue carbon under the Paris Agreement, and the progress made in assessing blue carbon ecosystems, this approach is now highly feasible, in particular if supported by risk reduction approaches such as the involvement of multilateral development banks.

Risk: Coastal spaces compete for multiple uses, so unless this investment takes place at scale there is a risk that we lose more of these ecosystems to development.

6. Financing coastal risk reduction

Description:

Risks of coastal inundation are rapidly rising globally as a consequence of the cumulative impacts of rising seas and severe storms associated with climate change, combined with anthropogenic alteration to watersheds and coastal ecosystems. On the seaward side of coastal margins, the value that coastal ecosystems (e.g., reefs, seagrasses, mangroves) provide worldwide for reducing storm surge-related flood risk amounts to billions of dollars per year in averted losses to infrastructure and livelihoods (World Bank 2016): mangroves alone provide global flood protection benefits exceeding US\$65 billion per year (Menendez et al. 2020). From the landward side, the flood control and nutrient cycling services provided by wetlands prevent downstream damage to coastal infrastructure and industries (Mitsch and Gosselink 2000; Turner and Daily 2008). These costs are rarely factored into decision-making that has enabled large-scale clearing and alteration of wetland hydrology for coastal development and extractive activities. Taking these costs into account also has the potential to save the lives and livelihoods of millions of people threatened by coastal risks.

Making these costs transparent through coastal ecosystem valuation is the first step towards financing solu-

tions that are required to implement wetland protection and restoration at the scale required to maintain and restore flood mitigation services. For example, the Restoration Insurance Service Company (RISCO) is being established as a social enterprise designed to assess and monetize the coastal asset risk reduction (and blue carbon) value of mangroves in order to finance mangrove conservation and restoration (Figure 5). RISCO will identify and verify areas of mangroves with high value for coastal protection and effectively sell this information to insurance companies who can then pass on reduced premiums to coastal asset owners to incentivize actions that sustain mangrove conservation. In another example, stakeholders in the Mexican state of Quintana Roo, including the state government, hotel owners, The Nature Conservancy and the National Parks Commission, have established a Coastal Zone Management Trust, which is designed to collect funds from different sources to carry out reef maintenance and repair. The Trust, which includes both government and private sector representatives, has purchased the world's first coral reef insurance policy. Insurance payouts will be made to finance reef and beach repair and maintenance should wind speeds in excess of 100 knots cause damage. Building on the success of the reef insurance policy in Mexico, there is an unprecedented opportunity to scale reef insurance globally. A key next step is the implemen-

tation of feasibility assessments, product development and stakeholder engagement in areas where interest in the approach is strongest. Potential countries include Honduras, Guatemala, Belize, Mexico, Indonesia, Philippines, and the United States.

Another type of vehicle that could operationalize financial flows for coastal wetland protection and restoration is through payments for watershed services (PWS). PWS operate through upstream watershed conservation and restoration financed by downstream water users, as well as other public and private sector entities (Bremer et al. 2018). PWS could be housed within trust funds established with the mandate to finance NbS and green-grey hybrid infrastructure that reduce coastal risk and improve water quality, while supporting biodiversity and climate adaptation benefits. With enough capital, such funds can become self-sustaining by generating internal revenue from investments, as well as through concessional loan programs. For example, a Watershed Security Fund has been proposed for British Columbia that would invest in the agencies, businesses and First Nation communities responsible for implementing NbS actions to maintain important watershed services, such as groundwater and surface flow regulation, erosion control, and water purification (POLIS/CBFLI/FNFC/BCWF 2019).

Figure 5. Diagram showing financing and operational structure of the Restoration Insurance Service Company (RISCO). (<https://www.climatefinancelab.org/project/coastal-risk-reduction/>)

Benefits:

Climate-benefit: NbS implemented to reduce coastal inundation risk can contribute to both mitigation and adaptation (particularly if focused on mangrove, seagrass or inland wetland, including riparian area, restoration). With respect to mitigation, as an example, the RISCO model is being piloted in the Philippines with the goal to provide a climate benefit of more than 600,000 tonnes of avoided and sequestered CO₂ emissions, and raised revenue of greater than US\$10M for mangrove conservation and restoration. If successfully scaled to Mexico, Malaysia, Indonesia and Brazil, which have contextual conditions suitable for replication, the RISCO model could generate more than US\$200M for mangrove protection and avoid emissions equivalent to the annual electricity use of over 2 million homes. With respect to adaptation, the measures are specifically designed to reduce flood risk.

Co-benefits: Wetland conservation and restoration has important co-benefits for health, food security, and livelihoods by improving fisheries habitats and reducing the spread of water-related disease (Jenkins and Jupiter 2015).

Equity and distribution: As flooding can disproportionately affect poor and marginalized communities, who often live in highly climate vulnerable areas where sea-level rise and coastal inundation are a significant threat, care needs to be taken that investments in NbS for coastal risk reduction are not just limited to areas of high infrastructure value (Atkinson et al. 2015). Like other solutions involving financial flows, attention should focus on equitable access and benefits sharing platforms, supported by controls that maintain transparency and accountability in funding distribution.

Timing of benefits: Benefits are likely to be fully realized on a decadal time scale, which will be the time required to create the operational environment for institutions to manage financial flows, enable appropriate, participatory consultation on the nature of investments, and, where restoration is implemented, the time required to yield full provision of coastal protection and flood mitigation services.

Feasibility and Risks:

Cost: Initial start-up costs may be high, but there is great potential for long-term sustainability and high impact outcomes at scale.

Return on investment: Despite initial high start-up costs, these mechanisms have potential to scale impacts across large geographic spaces and provide sustained benefits to large numbers of individuals.

Barriers: Ability to implement wetland conservation and restoration interventions will be affected by land and sea tenure regimes. Care needs to be taken to ensure the transparency and accountability of institutions controlling financial flows. The scale of financing will be heavily influenced by the willingness of the private sector to invest.

Feasibility: There is considerable guidance on implementation strategies for reducing risk through coastal wetland protection and restoration, but innovative financing mechanisms to enable scaling and durability are still in pilot stages.

Risk: Most risks lie in the start-up phases of establishing financing mechanisms, which require sufficient controls on transparency and accountability to secure confidence of investors.

Box 1: Blue biodiversity investment

The 2020 report “Financing Nature: Closing the global biodiversity financing gap” makes a persuasive case for biodiversity finance, yet the amount of blue biodiversity finance is very small. Unless we design appropriate investment mechanisms and financing incentives, we are at risk of losing vast blue biodiversity value. To take one example, the proposed BBNJ Agreement to protect biodiversity in the high seas has in its present draft no significant financial mechanism. The Convention on Biological Diversity is supported through the Global Environment Facility (GEF), but different to the Global Climate Fund, the GEF does not have comparable resources. Addressing these challenges through innovative approaches such as the creation of a targeted public private partnership, such as an Ocean Sustainability Bank, could provide a knowledge hub and financing tool (Thiele & Gerber, 2017) to support biodiversity conservation efforts through offering multiple financial products, ranging from debt to equity and including grants to deliver blended finance solutions to rapidly scale blue finance. Private sector blue impact investments into sustainable ocean solutions and concepts such as the Global Reef Fund, specifically focussed on opportunities to reduce drivers of threats to reefs, can help build blue biodiversity resilience.

Marine ecosystems face multiple pressures and are key to the earth climate system. The net positive impact of protecting natural ocean ecosystems from human pressures will be significant and can be quantified. To take one example, human activities are rapidly impacting the capacity of the ocean to act as a carbon sink. We need to use financial mechanisms to incentivise actions that help protect the key ecosystem components of the marine carbon sequestration chain and transition financial services to support a sustainable blue economy. Poor coastal communities are the most exposed to ocean change and would be primary beneficiaries of enhanced marine biodiversity support, allowing for instance for sustained access to natural resources at the local level (Hicks et al. 2019).

The Covid pandemic has shown that a lack of understanding of nature can create conditions that lead to large and urgent funding needs. Redirecting investment into nature can help to strengthen resilience. Raising awareness for the urgency to protect marine biodiversity and designing appropriate investment mechanisms and financial incentives can help to create conditions that allow us to invest in nature now rather than to be faced with far higher abatement cost in the future.

Box 2: The Tetiaroa project - Reconnecting Land-sea Nutrient Feedbacks to Enhance Island Ecosystem Resilience

This is our Working Group's contribution to a possible Blue Climate Initiative across-BCI proposal centred on a cross-cutting range of activities on Tetiaroa (and perhaps Moorea). It is not one of our formal proposed TOPSs, but we outline our proposed contribution within this Box.

Challenge: There are burgeoning research and policy interests in how animals play key roles in mediating ecosystem function and biogeochemistry, in both terrestrial and marine systems, at scales from local to planetary^{1,2}, and how these roles have been disrupted and can be restored. Cross-ecosystem nutrient subsidies driven by animals such as seabirds play a key role in the structure, dynamics, and resilience of interconnected ecological communities³, but modern human activities have disrupted these ecological linkages through over-exploitation, species introductions, and by creating physical barriers to connectivity. Seabirds are globally important drivers of nutrient cycling⁴, yet introduced rats have decimated their populations across 90% of the world's island chains⁵. Recent work has demonstrated that in the absence of rats, abundant seabird populations can enhance the productivity and functioning of adjacent coral reefs⁶. Eradicating human-introduced rats is a relatively simple management intervention -- though costly to successfully implement and also needs to be coupled with long-term biosecurity measures -- intended to restore seabird populations and island-reef nutrient cycles (Fig. 6). However, these nutrient pathways and the ecological cascade through the land-sea system are likely to be highly complex in space and time, presenting a significant challenge to detect and monitor the consequences of interventions across landscapes and seascapes.

Solution: There is a unique opportunity to conduct a 'natural experiment' on Tetiaroa, co-designed with managers, to coincide with an atoll-wide rat eradication to restore nutrient subsidies and ecosystem integrity. An integrated land-sea systems approach investigating the whole-site response to a single intervention to restore nutrient cycling has the potential to transform the way we understand and manage island ecosystems worldwide. Integrating and modeling data across scales will enable us to test the hypothesis that restoration of nutrient cycling and the ecological consequences that result can be remotely detected and modeled using cost-effective remote sensing technologies and spatial pattern analyses. The scientific approach proposed is unprecedented in its

ecological scope and technological sophistication, using chemical signatures at microbial scales, as well as innovative remote sensing technologies deployed underwater and from air and space to track and quantify changes across land and sea. The fundamental goal is to understand, for the first time, how restored nutrient flows within a connected land-sea ecosystem result in whole-system ecological change by quantifying the response of different trophic groups and ecosystem attributes over different temporal and spatial scales. The proposed project would quantify cross-ecosystem nutrient pathways before and after island restoration and reveal the consequences for local productivity and resilience, as well as the community structure and competitive dynamics between trophic groups. The results of this work will operationalize and scale island restoration efforts that restore land-sea nutrient feedback for optimal ecological and social outcomes supporting SDG 14 and the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021-2030).

Figure 6. How might restored nutrient cycles affect land-sea community dynamics and ecosystem resilience?

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 Blue Climate Initiative

The Blue Climate Initiative accelerates ocean-related strategies, collaborating across a multidisciplinary global community towards a restored and healthy climate; an understood and protected ocean; and resilient, thriving and equitable communities. The fiscal sponsor for the Blue Climate Initiative is Tetiaroa Society, a US 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization (tetiaroasociety.org).